

Greener Journal of Science, Engineering and Technological Research

ISSN: 2276-7835 Impact Factor 2012 (UJRI): 0.7563 ICV 2012: 5.62

Soil Development in Hyper Density, its Types and Factors Effective on Design of Hyper Density Method

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Hyper density method is one of the methods for permanent development of soil without adding foreign matter to soil which means leaving heavy gavels on the height. The term hyper density is derived from dynamic density of coarse-grained soils and dynamic strength of fine-grained soils and because these two methods are generally equal, the term hyper density has replaced it. High dynamic density, low energy density and dynamic replacement and mixture (DRM) are among the hyper density methods. Factors effective on design of this method depend on two important factors which include: soil factors, work equipment factors.

Keywords: Super compaction, DRM, permeability, drainage, depth of influence, optimum radius.

INTRODUCTION

Improvement of weak grounds is one of the geotechnical subjects which have attracted attention of many researchers. When encountering weak grounds, one of the methods below is usually selected to overcome the problem:

- Changing location of construction project from a place with weak materials to a place with appropriate conditions
- Removing inappropriate materials and replacing them with stronger materials
- Changing foundation design in the structure to a design compatible with geotechnical conditions of considered ground
- Soil improvement

First and second methods are not always possible and sometimes are even uneconomical. Ground improvement and modification of soil conditions is economically and technically preferred to the third method. In most of the projects, the cost of deep foundation execution is much more than soil improvement methods. The purpose of soil improvement is increasing soil load bearing capacity, decreasing ground settlement, decreasing soil porosity and increasing soil density, making uniform the deformability properties of materials and mitigation of inappropriate physical and chemical changes in soil.

Compaction by this method involves dropping a heavy pounder with weight of 5-20 tons from free height of up to 30 m. Actually, higher range of masses and drop heights can be used in different construction projects. For example, Gambian reported drop of a pounder with weight of 220 from height of 24 m.; masses up to 25t can be dropped from a specific height by a heavy crane with a lifting cable which can move freely. Free cable spool allows generation of a free fall. When heavier weights are used, the equipments are strengthened. Weights used in this method are generally made of metal plates; metal shells filled with concrete and reinforced concrete. Weights are usually square, circular and octagon. In this technique, loose granular soil layers are densified by high energy impacts which result in reduction of porosity, compaction of soil and ejection of liquids in cavities (if any).

Different Methods of Dynamic Compaction

2-1 deep (heavy) dynamic compaction: The procedure involves dropping heavy weights on a loose and compressible soil surface to improve mechanical properties of the soil. In this method the weights range from 10 to 25 tons and drop height range from 15 to 25 m. In technical literature this method is known by the general name dynamic compaction.

2-2 low energy dynamic compaction: It is not always needed to improve soil to high depths, for example for a soil containing a loose layer with thickness of several meters or when a small increase in bearing capacity is needed regardless of settlement. Low energy dynamic compaction or repeated compaction is a quick, economical and effective method for improving mechanical properties of loose soils. In this method, about 7 tons mass is dropped from height of approximately 2 m on a movable target. This method is effective for improving the ground up to 3-4m depth.

2-3 dynamic replacement and mixing: Recently, applications of heavy weights drops on very soft- to- soft cohesive clay soils containing granular columns for dynamic replacement have been extended. One of the initial endeavors for ground improvement by this technique was made in 1983 for quick transportation of materials in Bashan depot, Singapore. In this method, after producing DR columns by low energy impacts, dropping heavier weights leads to entrance of sand jets from these columns into the soil and this causes rupture in initial structure of loose soil such that its inherent secondary compaction properties are effectively dissipated.

Mechanisms of Soil compaction by DR and DRM methods

Effective Factors in Design of Dynamic Compaction Procedure

Some researchers such as Lounge and Lukas (1986) classified factors influencing efficiency and depth of improvement by dynamic compaction into two groups:

1. 3-1 factors associated with ground including soil type and layers, presence of a hard layer below or top of the soil under compaction, degree of saturation and underground water level.
2. 3-2 factors associated with compaction instruments such as pounder weight, pounder drop height, area of pounder base, pounder shape, the number of impacts and the number of pulses.

Factors associated with ground include:

Different Types of Soils in Applications of Dynamic Compaction

3-1-1 granular soils: When an impact is applied to the soil, a hard deposit is suddenly formed below the pounder. However, the main beneficial effect is obtained at higher depths by high energy waves in the ground, energy density is maximum on vertical symmetry axis and it reduces as the angle from this axis increases. Also as the wave penetrates, semispherical front of the wave is enlarged and energy density significantly reduces. In granular soils such as sand, grit and cobblestone, soil improvement mechanism is easily understood. Displacement of the particles toward each other and partly low frequency vibratory movements cause porosity coefficient to decrease and soil relative density to increase. Consequently, bearing capacity is increased and settlement is reduced. The amount of attenuation and propagation of compressive waves defines the zone of compacted soil; although some part of wave's energy is dissipated through nonlinear processes which occur at impact point neighborhoods and some part remains inside the weight which rebounds. However, there is no information about the share of compressive, shear and Rayleigh waves in dynamic compaction energy, studies by Miller and Pursey showed that for low depth foundations with flat base due to permanently stable vibration the shares of Rayleigh, compressive and shear waves in energy transfer are 67%, 27% and 6%, respectively.

3-1-2 cohesive soils: Before having effectively carried out heavy tamping on saturated clay soil, the researchers believed that it was impossible to consolidate it satisfactorily. However it was observed that these materials settled instantly several tens of centimeters. Menard for the first time proposed a theory for dynamic consolidation. He conducted some experiments using dynamic oedometer device which he patented. The experiment results clarified mechanisms involved in dynamic consolidation. Fournier also conducted some experiment using dynamic oedometer. His report indicated that the involved mechanisms include sudden settlement, quick dissipation of pore water pressure and recovery of thixotropic resistance.

Dynamic consolidation like dynamic compaction is performed by repeated drop of heavy weights from height of 15 to 40 m on specific points. The difference between dynamic consolidation and dynamic compaction is that the number of phases or the number of drops, time lag between phases and consecutive drops as well as grid spacing (distance between impact points) must be determined in the presented plan. This time lag is necessary to allow pore water pressure produced during pervious impacts to dissipate and prevent its excessive increase during consolidation process. Menard & Bruise believed that studying below processes is essential for better understanding of mechanisms involved in dynamic consolidation.

Compressibility of Saturated Soils Due to Presence of Fine Air Bubbles

Fine-grained saturated soils are considered as incompressible when subjected to rapid loadings. According to Terzaghi's theory, evacuation of water is the necessary and sufficient condition for producing settlement due to volume changes. But early observations indicate that an impact of pounder always leads to an immediate settlement. Later studies revealed that most quaternary soils contain gas in the form of micro-bubbles. This gas content ranges from 1 to 4 percent of soil volume. It seems that the equilibrium conditions of these bubbles are modified as a result of an impact and new equilibrium conditions cause soil to be compressed. As a first approximation, it can be assumed that volume changes of these bubbles are governed by Mariott & Henry's laws.

The Gradual Liquefaction Under Repeated Impacts

Due to repetitive applications of loads to soil mass, the gas present in soil gradually becomes compressed such that the percentage of gas by volume approaches zero. Under this condition, the soil reacts as an incompressible material and liquefaction of the soil takes place. The energy level required for this stage is known as 'saturation energy'. In practice, liquefaction in soils often occurs gradually because most natural deposits are composed of layers with various properties and the silty or sandy parts liquefy before the clayey layers.

The Changes of Permeability of a Soil Mass Due to the Creation of Fissure

A particular phenomenon observed on sites which are improved by dynamic consolidation is the initial rapid reduction of pore-water pressure which cannot be explained by low permeability measured before dynamic consolidation. When sandy soils are subject to large hydraulic gradients, their permeability values are very high. This phenomenon is general in all soils. A slight local increase in pore-water pressure results in tearing and splitting of the solid tissues and pore-water flows through these newly created fissures. Drop of poulder on regular grid locations causes creation of horizontal and regular fissures around the impact points. Existing regularity in tamping points results in formation of continuous channels in the soil. It has also been observed empirically in the laboratory that the coefficient of permeability increases when the intergranular stresses decrease and that it reaches the maximum value when the soil becomes liquid. During a dynamic consolidation operation due to very high pore-water pressures effective intergranular stresses decrease and permeability increases.

Thixotropic Recovery

It seems that waves due to impact cause the adsorbed water to transform into free water. Therefore, cross section of capillary channels is enlarged. The reverse phenomenon occurs when thixotropy takes place. During a tamping operation, a considerable fall in shear strength is first noted; the minimum being recorded when the soil is liquefied or approaching liquefaction. As pore-water pressure dissipates, a large increase in shear strength and deformation modulus is observed; this is due to the closer contact between the particles as well as the gradual fixation of new layers of adsorbed water. This phenomenon is apparent in all fine soils especially sensitive clays.

3-1-3 fine Ograined soils with moisture content:

Despite earlier discussions, generally the more of fines content in a granular soil deposit, the less efficient will be dynamic compaction of the soil. Experiences show that by increasing fines content more than 10 %, the efficiency of dynamic compaction is reduced. Mitchell's studies indicated that when percentage of clay is more than 15%, dynamic compaction by dropping a weight is ineffective because the permeability of materials is too low to allow rapid dissipation of pore water pressures. In addition, soil structure is not easily fractured due to interaction between water and soil particles. When selecting dynamic compaction characteristics, some soil properties such as moisture condition (the degree of saturation of soil), permeability and drainage path length for saturated soils are most important. Lukas classified soils into three categories ranging from suitable to unsuitable for dynamic compaction. This classification was made based on grain size: group 1: pervious soils, group 2: semipervious soils and group 3: impervious soils.

Group 1: Dynamic compaction works best on soils where the degree of saturation is low, the permeability of the soil mass is high, and drainage is good. When the impact energy is transferred to ground surface, the soil starts to become compressed by ejecting air from its pores. Air exits the soil much easier than water; this is due to its lower viscosity. If degree of saturation of soil is low (70 to 95%), a continuous flow of air is formed through pores and if the degree of saturation is high, air bubbles are formed inside the water and consequently soil will show a behavior similar to saturated soils. In this group, permeability is more than 10^{-3} cm/s. grain sizes range from rubble to sand. For example building rubble, some mine spoil, some industrial waste fill such as slag, and decomposed deposits are appropriate for dynamic compaction. Dynamic compaction is effective for all soils of group 1, even saturated ones; this is due to their high permeability and rapid dissipation of excess pore water pressure.

Group 2: Includes soils whose permeability ranges from 10^{-6} to 10^{-3} cm/s. silts, sandy silts and clayed silts with $PI < 8$ fall into this group. Dynamic compaction is easily carried out on these soils if they are semi-saturated, although dissipation of excess pore-water may last some days which need correct and accurate design of dynamic compaction procedure. This means that sufficient time should be allowed between the phases to allow excess pore water pressures to dissipate.

Group 3: Includes almost impervious soils (permeability is less than 10^{-6} cm/s). Clayey soils whose clay content is more than 25% and PI is greater than 8 needs long time for dissipation of excess pore water pressures generated during dynamic compaction which increase time period of the project. This time period can be reduced by shortening drainage paths. If the water content of the clayey soils prior to dynamic compaction is less than the plasticity index of the soil, improvement can be carried out in these soils by dynamic compaction before the deposits become fully saturated. After saturation occurs, no further improvement will be realized regardless of the amount of energy applied.

Factors associated with instrument include:

3-2-1 Pounder Weight

The influence of an increase in pounder weight on increased improvement of soil can be explained by influence of an increase in momentum on an increased efficiency of transferred energy to the ground. For a specific energy per impact, using a heavier weights and smaller drop heights result in an increase in momentum. Experiments conducted by Takada & Oshima showed that depth of the improved zone is usually between 10 to 12 m and its radius ranges from 5 to 7 m. Based on these values, the mass of compacted zone is on the order 100 tons which is heavier than pounders and usually used in dynamic compaction projects. Even if some parts of this mass partake in impact process at each moment, soil equivalent mass is (or is not??) comparable with pounder mass. It can be easily found that the more the impact momentum, the more energy transfers to the ground. Therefore, at a specific level of energy per impact, an increase in momentum will lead to an increase in efficiency of the compaction operation.

3-2-2 Pounder Drop Height

It should be noted that, as a matter of importance, momentum is not contrary to earlier experiments which related energy per impact to the depth and degree of improvement as applied energy still plays a key role in determination of the degree to which soil properties improve. Therefore, as drop height and consequently pounder velocity and applied kinetic energy increase, depth and degree of improvement can be increased. Furthermore, in saturated soils, if impact velocity is greater than velocity of waves transferring in liquefied soil, the efficiency of energy increases. On the other hand, due to economic and technical reasons, contractors are inclined to increase drop height. For the same initial density the more drop height, the greater depth of produced crater and for the same drop height, the more density, and the smaller depth of crater.

Compaction curves obtained from impact of poulder with the ground

3-2-3 Influence of Poulder Shape

According to Vanimpe, poulder shape (hydraulic radius) plays an important role in dynamic compaction of soils. This parameter has not been fully investigated. The general shape of poulder in the majority of dynamic compaction projects is cylindrical with a flat base. Feng and Chen proposed a new idea for poulder shape. They conducted various experiments on two types of sand in dry and saturated conditions. In these experiments, one flat base poulder and one conical base poulder were used. Shear can be produced in ground surface by tapping an inclined surface on soil surface. Therefore, the share of shear waves in total applied energy can be increased using a conical poulder. Experiments performed using two poulders showed that although achieving a better compaction using conical shape poulder depends on aggregation characteristics and volume change behavior of sand, using this shape of poulders results in an efficiency equal to or better than flat base poulders.

3-2-4 Poulder Base Area

Earlier observations indicated that an increase in poulder base area results in an increase in radius of compacted zone (Harada & suluki, Chow et al). Yong used a one-dimensional model and reported that depth of improved zone crater decreases as poulder base area increases and this was attributed to distribution of impact load over a larger zone. But two-dimensional finite element model proposed by Gu and Lee suggest an optimum value for poulder base area at a specific weight, which is contrary to Yong's reports. In fact, if poulder radius is very small, horizontal confinement of the soil column below impact location just remains unchanged for a short time. Therefore, the depth at which one-dimensional wave propagates become limited. In addition, Gu and Lee indicated that optimum radius for poulder base is increased as energy and momentum increases at each impact. Also influence of poulder base radius at regions adjacent to impact location is more because these regions are much more influenced by one-dimensional pressure conditions.

3-2-5 The Number of Drops

As the number of drops is increased, stress level at various points increases; this is due to an increase in soil stiffness. Stress level of stress wave is a function of wave velocity which itself is a function of soil stiffness. Therefore, as compaction process proceeds, soil stiffness increases and then an increase is observed in stress level at a specific location as the number of drops increases. Maximum influence of soil particles during first impact is less than subsequent impacts because soil is initially very soft, therefore the first impact is longer and is accompanied by smaller maximum force. Maximum accelerations during second and third impacts are approximately the same. Excess depth of soil improvement during subsequent impacts is due to the facts that contact time is shortened and less energy is adsorbed at top layers, although the influence of the number of drops reduces as depth of influence increases. Results of studies performed by Taakada & shima and Mayneetal showed that most of the produced settlements occur before initial 20 impacts. It should be noted that clayey soils improvement needs more impacts comparing to granular soils.

3-2-6 Grid Spacing

Grid spacing or distance between points of impact in a compaction grid, influences total energy in a site. Today practical parameters of dynamic compaction such as poulder characteristics, falling height, the number of impacts per pass and grid spacing are determined based on designer's experience and supplementary field experiments.

Initial grid spacing generally approximates the thickness of the compressible layer. Incorrect selection of energy level and spacing results in a dense upper layer, making it difficult or impossible to treat loose material below.

Contour lines of $b\phi\Delta / \Delta\phi$ for a grid with $s/d=2.5$

Tamping grid with grid spacing equal to $2.5D$

3-2-7 Different Passes

Dynamic compaction operation is usually executed in several phases (passes) on a grid pattern (triangular or square). Square grid pattern is more common and second phase grid is considered such that centers of spaces between two adjacent points overlap those in first pass grid. Pounders with circular and octagonal cross sections are suitable for initial phases because less energy is dissipated in formation of circular opening. For applications under water table, special shapes are designed for increasing falling velocity in water. Depending on soil conditions, two or more phases are used in this method and grid spacing becomes smaller in each phase to achieve necessary improvement. After each pass, usually the imprints are backfilled with surrounding soils. Sometimes, it is necessary to maintain the working platform at a constant level throughout the work. For instance where groundwater level is high, the crater is backfilled with imported coarse-grained materials. The initial passes are called high energy phases because compactive energy is concentrated on points with distance of about 3 m. Completion of the high energy phase is usually followed by a low energy phase, called "ironing,". Applied energy during this final phase is less than first phase. The purpose of this compaction is densifying superficial layers.

Degree of soil improvement by dynamic compaction

Some reports such as those presented by Menard & Broise (1975), Leonards (1981) and Chow (1994) suggest successful execution of dynamic compaction operation in many projects. Dynamic compaction efficiency can be expressed in terms of propagation of zone of influence in horizontal or vertical direction. One important parameter which is considered for indicating the degree of soil improvement by dynamic compaction is depth of influence (DI). This depth is actually the maximum thickness of the layer which is treated by this method. Since soil improvement is

a function of its particles vibration, propagation and attenuation of compressive waves determines the zone of compacted soil. Berment & Selby defined soil improvement zone as the depth at which vibration penetrates until maximum vertical acceleration of the particle exceeds 2g.

Oshima & Takada defined depth of influence as the depth of ground at which increase in relative density does not exceed 5%. Since applied energy is one of important parameters in design process, many studies were performed by various researchers to estimate depth of influence considering the amount of applied energy. For instance, Menard (1975) proposed below equation for calculating depth of influence:

$$DI = \sqrt{WH}$$

Where w denotes pounder weight in terms of ton and H represents drop height in meter. Later, Loonards (1980) suggested using a coefficient equal to 0.5 at right side of the equation to have a better agreement between results and the measured values. Mayneetal reported that this coefficient can range from 0.3 to 0.8. Then Lukas (1992) announced that for pervious granular layers this coefficient can vary between 0.5 and 0.6. The variation in n shows that some other factors as well as energy per impact affect depth of influence. Some of these factors include:

- 1- The drop mechanism of the crane.
- 2- Total amount of energy applied.
- 3- Type of soil deposit being densified.
- 4- Presence of energy absorbing layers.
- 5- Presence of a hard layer above or below the soil being treated.
- 6- Contact pressure of the tamper

Therefore, the equation was modified as:

$$DI = n\sqrt{WH}$$

Mayneetal showed that in some sites the coefficient n can be as large as unit. Lukas (1986) indicated that repeated tamping on a location improves the amount of compaction in the zone but the depth of influence does not increase. He also summarized some recommended values for coefficient n in a Table. Using the values presented in this Table is conducive to an acceptable estimation of depth of influence. But some other factors which will be described may influence these initial values. The pounder must have a flat and smooth bottom because contact pressure is equal to force divided by pounder surface area. In order to use values presented in this table, contact pressure must range from 800 to 1550 lb/ft² (40 to 77.5 kN/m²). Generally low contact pressures are more suitable for compaction of top layers. Saturated clay layers are more inclined to absorb energy, therefore if there is a thick and loose clay layer below tamping point or near it, the depth of improvement will be reduced. In contrast, hard or cemented layers are inclined to distribute impact energy over a wider area; this leads to dissipation of some parts of impact energy. Also, a hard layer located below the loose soil has a favorable effect in reflecting energy back upward into the soil resulting in a greater degree of improvement. Luongo presented some empirical linear equations for calculating the depth of influence based on the information gathered from 30 sites:

$$DI = K_1 + K_2(W.H)$$

Where K_1 and K_2 are called depth constant and energy constant, respectively. He indicated that K_1 can vary between 1.01 and 2 and K_2 can range from 0.009 to 0.016. He also defined the degree of soil improvement as:

$$\eta_{EM} = \frac{E_m(\text{after treatment})}{E_m(\text{befoer treatment})}$$

$$\eta_{PL} = \frac{P_L(\text{after treatment})}{P_L(\text{befoer treatment})}$$

E_m : pressuremeter modulus

P_L : pressuremeter limit pressure

Van & Derouck presented another method for determining the degree of improvement by dynamic compaction using a dropping weight. They expressed the degree of improvement can be expressed in terms of ratio of areas beneath

CPT curves for cone resistance as a soil property which is variable with depth. The degree of improvement reaches its maximum value at a depth called critical depth. By further increase in depth the degree of improvement will be

reduced to maintain soil properties at the depth of influence unchanged. A review on available data indicates that critical depth is half of maximum depth of influence.

CONCLUSIONS

1. In particular, supercompaction methods such as DR and DRM, granular materials are mixed with fine-grained soils and consequently fine-grained soil is modified.
2. Supercompaction method is effective for all high pervious soils ($K > 10^{-3}$) with $PI < 8$, even if saturated.
3. Supercompaction is useful for impervious soils ($K < 10^{-6}$) with $PI > 8$ before the deposits become fully saturated. After saturation occurs, no further improvement will be realized.
4. According to Terzaghi's theory, fine-grained saturated soils are considered as incompressible when subjected to rapid loadings. Evacuation of water is the necessary and sufficient condition for producing settlement, this settlement is known as immediate settlement. In practice, this (چه چیزیه؟) leads to higher compaction due to presence of air bubbles inside the soil.
5. Sandy, silty and clayey soils are the most favorable soils for this soil improvement method.
6. There are two basic solutions for preventing transfer of vibration to adjacent structures:
 - a. Application of spring-dampers between the machinery and foundation of the device producing vibration
 - b. Preventing the transfer of vibration to adjacent structures by digging a ditch or trench around vibrator foundation.

In the first method, dampers including rubber cushions, springs, cushions filled with compressed air, and combinations of spring and other shock absorbers prevent the direct transfer of vibration of the machinery to its foundation. In the second method, a trench with suitable width and depth is dug around the vibration source and it is filled with bentonite mud.
7. The total energy applied for soil improvement should not exceed soil saturation energy; otherwise liquefaction occurs in the soil.
8. Thixotropy is transformation of water adsorbed by soil grains into free water due to waves produced by impact. This phenomenon leads to a reduction in soil shear resistance.
9. Experiences showed that by increasing fines content more than 10 %, the efficiency of dynamic compaction is reduced. Other studies indicated that when percentage of clay is more than 15%, dynamic compaction by dropping a weight is ineffective.
10. The depth of influence is expressed by equation $DI = WH$. For better agreement with experimental measurements, this equation is multiplied by a coefficient, n , which depends on soil type and its permeability.
11. The depth of improvement is a function of poulder weight and drop height. Poulder base area which is a factor associated with work instruments plays the most important role in optimum radius of compaction.

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